
Our Contributors

A. Alangaram. SJ: A. Alangaram is a Professor of Theology and superior of Berchmans Illam, an International study house for Jesuits in formation, Loyola College Campus, Chennai. He holds a Doctorate in Theology from the Catholic Theology Faculty of Leopold-Franzens-Universitaet, Innsbruck. He has been a Recognised Doctoral Guide by the Madras University for Doctoral Programmes in IDCR since 2004. His works include *Christ of the Asian Peoples; Religions for Societal Transformation and Empowering the Dalits and Poor in the Power of the Spirit*. He is a visiting professor in Madras University, Chennai, Vidyajyoti, Delhi, Dharmaram Vidya Kshetram, Bangalore, Don Bosco Theology Centre, Tiruvallur, Jnana Bharati Regional Theologate, Varanasi, Arulkadal, Jesuit Regional Theologate Chennai, and the Catholic Theology Faculty of Leopold-Franzens-Universitaet, Innsbruck, Austria. Email: alanarsj@gmail.com. ORCID: 0000-0001-6091-3707.

Ginish Cheruparambil Baby: He had worked with Motilal Oswal Securities as a research economist and currently working in Christ University, Lavasa as an Assistant Professor of Economics. He had been associated with Christ College, Pune and Symbiosis International University. His doctoral thesis is on Amartya Sen. Email: ginishcheruparambil@gmail.com. ORCID: 0000-0003-1081-2363.

Isaac Parackal OIC: Isaac Parackal is a Professor of Philosophy who holds a doctorate in philosophy from the University of St. Thomas Aquinas in Rome. At Present, he is teaching at Jnana-Deepa

Vidyapeeth in the faculty of Philosophy, Pune. He has authored a number of books and articles in philosophy and ecology and other secular subjects. He is a visiting faculty in different seminaries and secular institutions. E-mail: isaacparackal13@gmail.com. ORCID: 0000-0002-1527-1941.

Jacob Parappally, MSFS: Jacob Parappally holds a doctorate in Theology from the University of Freiburg, Germany. He was teaching systematic theology at Jnana Deepa, Pune for 14 years where he served as the dean of the Faculty of Theology. He is a visiting professor of many theological faculties in India and abroad. He was the Rector of Tejas Vidya Peetha, Institute of Mission-Oriented and Contextual Theology, Bangalore and was the President of the Indian Theological Association (2005-2011). He is the author of *Emerging Trends in Indian Christology*, *The Meaning of Jesus Christ: An Introduction to Christology*, *A Way of the Cross for Today* and the editor or co-editor of another 10 books. He translated the second book on Jesus Christ by Pope Benedict to Malayalam. He published more than 200 theological articles. He is the chief-editor of the Journal of Indian Theology. E-Mail: Jacob.Para@gmail.com. ORCID: 0000-0002-6943-7046

P. T. Joseph, SJ: He has Ph.D. in Electrical and Computer Engineering from Marquette University, MTh from JDV, Pune, M.B.A. from Saint Josephs University, Philadelphia, M.Sc. (Physics) from Madras University. He was a professor at XLRI Jamshedpur for 11 years, Professor and Director of XIM Bhubaneswar for 9 years, Director of the Pastoral Management program at Jnana Deepa, Pune, for 5 years and Director of Marian International Institute of Management for 5 years. In 2019 he was ‘Wade Chair Professor’ at Marquette University, USA teaching Artificial Intelligence. In 2020, he was ‘McLane Chair Professor’ at Saint Joseph’s University, Philadelphia teaching Artificial Intelligence. Email: ptjoesj@gmail.com ORCID: 0000-0003-3365-2374

Konrad J. Noronha, SJ: Konrad J. Noronha is the Director of the Center for Safeguarding - CCP Unit, at De Nobili College, Pune, India, Director and Coordinator of the Pastoral Management Program at Jnana Deepa, Pune, India, and co-convener of the Safeguarding Commission of the Jesuit Conference of South Asia. He has a Mas-

ters in Clinical Mental Health Counseling from Loyola University Maryland and a Masters in Systematic Theology from Vidyajyoti College of Theology, Delhi. His Doctorate is in Counselor Education and Supervision from Loyola University, Maryland. He is a visiting scholar to the Institute of Psychology, Pontifical Gregorian University, Rome, Italy. He is a licensed homeopathic physician (BHMS). He is actively involved in counseling and spiritual direction and has given talks, conducted workshops and retreats, and has audibles, book chapters, articles, and peer reviews to his credit. E-Mail: kjnoronha2000@gmail.com. ORCID: 0000-0002-8391-9762.

Kuruvilla Pandikattu, SJ: Kuruvilla Pandikattu is a professor of Physics, Philosophy and Religion at Jnana Deepa, Pune. Currently, he is the Dean of Faculty of Philosophy. He has been actively involved in dialogue between science and religion. Author of more than 36 books and 160 articles, Pandikattu is a Jesuit priest belonging to Dumka-Raiganj Province, India. He has been involved in organising national and international conferences on science-religion dialogue. Main topics of his research are: anthropology, eschatology, life-management and transhumanism. E-Mail: kuru@kuru.in; kuru@jdv.edu.in; www.kuru.in. ORCID: 0000-0001-9815-3707.

Manickam Irudayaraj, SJ: Manickam Irudayaraj is a Jesuit belonging to Gujarat Province. He did his Licentiate in Scripture at Pontifical Biblical Institute in Rome and doctorate in Biblical Theology at Vidya Jyoti College of Theology, Delhi. He was a member of the staff at Gujarat Vidya Deep, the Regional Theologate at Vadodara. He has also taught as visiting professor at Jnana Deepa, Pune; VJ, Delhi, and other regional centres of theology at Bhopal, Patna, Ranchi and Varanasi. At present, as an emeritus, he is teaching Scripture at Vidya Jyoti, Delhi. E-Mail: mirajsj@gmail.com. ORCID: 0000-0002-7967-1653.

Richard Lopes SJ: Richard Lopes is a Jesuit of Gujarat Province, and currently teaching Systematic Theology at the Faculty of Theology, Jnana Deepa, Pune. He defended his Thesis titled *Indian Christology of the Way*, in 2010 at the Faculty of Theology in LFU Innsbruck in 2010, and it was awarded with the 'Karl-Rahner Prize for Theological Research' in 2011 by Karl Rahner Foundation, Innsbruck and published by Innsbrucker Theologische Studien,

Tyrolia - Innsbruck. After completing the Doctorate in Innsbruck, he had been teaching Systematic Theology in the Gujarat Vidya Deep in Gujarat till 2018, while residing in a parish and was actively involved in pastoral ministry. E-Mail: richylopes@gmail.com. ORCID: 0000-0002-3050-2365.

Saurabh Todariya is currently working in Consciosuenss Studies Program, National Institute of Advanced Studies (Bangalore). He has completed his PhD from JNU (New Delhi). His research intrests include Phenomenology, Poststructuralism and Critical Philosophy. Currently, he is exploring the relationship between embodiment, technology and religion. Email:saurabhtodariya.jnu@gmail.com. ORCID: 0000-0002-3291-2237.

Thomas Karimundackal, SJ: Thomas Karimundackal teaches Old Testament and biblical languages at the Faculty of Theology, Jnana Deepa, Pune, and currently serves as the Head of the Department of Scripture Studies, and coordinator of the Masters Programme in Biblical Studies at Jnana Deepa. He has presented several research papers in many national and international conferences, and published many books, and articles in national and international Journals as well as in edited books. He is also a visiting faculty in many seminaries and colleges in India and abroad. E-mail: tomksj@gmail.com. ORCID: 0000-0001-7566-4504.

George Soares-Prabhu in Wikipedia: Please see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/George_Soares-Prabhu
For **quotes** by George M. **Soares Prabhu**, please see https://en.wikiquote.org/wiki/Soares-Prabhu,_George

JD Philosophy Series

- Salvino Azzopardi: *Epistemology and Phenomenology of Religions* (2018)
- Kuruvilla Pandikattu & Thomas Karimundackal (eds): *Melodies from the Flute: For Prof Noel Sheth SJ* (2018)
- Kurien Kunnumpuram: *Freedom and Joy* (2018)
- Cyril Desbruslais SJ: *Postmodernity: An Indian Christian Philosophical Appraisal* (2019)
- Cyril Desbruslais SJ: *Metaphysics: Philosophy of Be-ing for Today* (2019)
- John Peter Vallabadoss: *Indian Thinkers: Modern and Contemporary Period* (2019)
- Thomas Karimundackal & Kuruvilla Pandikattu (eds): *Logic and Love: For Prof John Vattanky SJ* (2019)
- Fabian Jose UMI: *Relevance of Thomas Merton's Spirituality for the Consecrated Life in India* (2019)
- Kuruvilla Pandikattu & PT Mathew (eds): *Committed to the Church and the Country: For Prof Kurien Kunnumpuam SJ* (2019)
- Cyril Desbruslais SJ: *The Philosophy of God: Faith and Traditions* (2019)
- Thomas Karimundackal & Kuruvilla Pandikattu (eds): *Fully Spiritual, Fully Human: For Dr Stephen Chundamthadam SJ* (2019)
- Kuruvilla Pandikattu (ed) *Fully Human and Fully Alive: Essays on Being Human Today in Honour of Dr Cyril Desbruslais SJ* (2020)
- Thomas Karimundackal SJ & Dolichan Kollareth SJ (eds) *Reason: Faithful and True: For Dr. George Karuvelil SJ* (2020)
- Kuruvilla Pandikattu SJ, Sebastian Vazhapilly SJ & Prasad Lankapilly SJ (eds) *Serving the Church and the Nation: Gratefully and Faithfully* (2020)
- Kuruvilla Pandikattu (ed) *Befriending the Other: Other Religions* (2021)
- Gargi Mukherjee: *Emancipation of the Wretched of the Earth*
- Cyril Desbruslais: *Ancient, Medieval and Modern Philosophy*
- Cyril Desbruslais: *Contemporary Philosophy* (2021)

***Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of
Religious Studies***

OFFICIALS

Chief Editor

**Prof Dr Kuruvilla
Pandikattu Joseph**

Dean, Faculty of Philosophy, Jnana Deepa
(JD), Pune 411014, India

Associate Editor

Dr Thomas Karimundackal

Associate Professor, Faculty of Theology,
Jnana Deepa (JD), Pune 411014, India

Book Review Editor

**Prof Dr Nishant A.
Irudayadason**

Professor, Faculty of Philosophy, JD

Editorial Board Members

Dr. Laxmikanta Padhi

Head, Department of Philosophy,
University of North Bengal,
Darjeeling-734013, West Bengal

Dr Sony Chundattu

Director, Christ College, Pune 411014

Biju Joseph MTH

Librarian, JD

Dr Dinesh Braganza

Ass Professor, Faculty of Philosophy, JD

Prof Dr Francis Gonsalves

President & Prof, Fac of Theology, JD

Consulting Editors

Dr Fabian Jose

Moderator, Center for Women's Studies,
JD

Dr Francis Pudhicherry

Ass Professor, Faculty of Theology, JD

Dr Gregory Arokiasamy

Ass Professor, Faculty of Theology, JD

Dr Henry D'Almeida

Ass Professor, Faculty of Philosophy, JD

Dr Herman Tirkey

Ass Professor, Faculty of Theology, JD

Dr Basaweshwar Mudagi

Former Head, Dept of Mathematics, Nowrosjee
Wadia College, Pune 411001; Sectional Recorder for
Mathematical Section 2021, 2022. Indian Science
Congress Association

Dr Isaac Parackal

Ass Professor, Faculty of Philosophy, JD

Dr. Kamaladevi Kunkolienker

Ass Prof of Philosophy, P.E.S. R.S.N. College of
Arts and Science, Farmagudi, Ponda Goa

Dr Jesuraj Rayappan

Ass Professor, Faculty of Theology, JD

Prof Dr John Karuvelil

Dean and Professor, Faculty of Theology, JD

Dr Jose Thayil

Registrar, JD

Dr Konrad Noranha

Ass Professor, Faculty of Theology, JD

Dr Louis Levill

Ass Professor, Faculty of Theology, JD

Dr Mariapushpam Paul Raj

Ass Professor, Faculty of Theology, JD

Prof Dr Mohan Doss

Professor, Faculty of Theology, JD

Dr Patricia Santos

Ass Professor, Faculty of Theology, JD

Dr Richard Lopes

Ass Professor, Faculty of Theology, JD

Dr S. Stephen Jayard

Professor, Faculty of Philosophy, JD

Prof Dr Selva Rathinam

Professor, Faculty of Theology, JD

Dr Shiju Joseph

Ass Professor, Faculty of Philosophy, JD

Dr Vadappuram M. Jose

Ass Professor, Faculty of Theology, JD

Dr Victor Sagayam

Ass Professor, Faculty of Theology, JD

Dr Anita Patankar

Director, Symbiosis School for Liberal Arts,
Pune 411014

Dr Shashikala Gурpur

Dean, Faculty of Law, Symbiosis Law School,
Pune 411014

Dr Vishal Yadav

Associate Professor in Sociology, Tilak
Maharashtra Vidyapeeth, Pune 411037

Advisory Board Members

Prof Dr Babu Joseph,

Former Vice-Chancellor, Cochin University
of Science and Technology (CUSAT), Kochi

**Prof Dr Carlos Augusto
Casanova Guerra,**

Universidad de Santo Tomas, Santiago Chile

**Prof Dr Carlos Miguel Gomez
Rincon,**

El Rosario University, Bogota Colombia

Prof Dr Chae-Yong Kim,

President (2014-16), Korean Association for
Religious Studies

Prof Dr Chris Baglow,

Notre Dame Seminary, New Orleans, LA, USA

Prof Dr Donald Frohlich,

University of St. Thomas (Emeritus), Houston,
TX, USA

Prof Dr Felix Raj,

Vice-Chancellor, St Xavier's University,
Kolkatta

Prof Dr George Pattery,

Former Vice-Chancellor, JD

Prof Dr Kamal Misra,

Vice-Chancellor, Utkal University of Culture

Prof Dr Louis Caruana,

Former Dean, Faculty of Philosophy,
Gregorian University, Rome, Italy

Prof Dr Maribel Nonato,

University of St. Thomas, Manila, Philippines

Prof Dr Paul Fernandes,

Former Vice-Chancellor, Xavier University,
Bhubaneswar

Dr Paul Parathazham,

Director, St John's National Academy of Health
Sciences, Bengaluru

Prof Dr Philippe Quentin,

University of Bordeaux, France

Prof Dr Raul Melendez,

Nacional Universidad, Bogota, Colombia

Prof Dr Rubén Herce Fernández,

University of Navarra, Spain

Prof Dr Savarimuthu Ignaci,

Former Vice-Chancellor, University of Madras
and Coimbatore

Prof Dr Sonajharia Minz,

Vice-Chancellor, Sido Kanhu Murmu
University, Dumka

Prof Dr Stephen Mavelly,

Former Vice-Chancellor, Assam Don Bosco
University, Guwahati

Prof Dr Renu Jain,

Vice-Chancellor, Devi Ahilya Vishwa
Vidhyalaya, Indore

**Rev. Fr. Jerome Stanislaus
D'Souza, SJ,**

Vice-Chancellor, JD

Publisher

Prof Dr Kuruvilla

Pandikattu Joseph

Faculty of Philosophy, JD

For details, please see
punejournal.in/officials

CODEN: JNANAR | OCLC: 39746721 | IXTHEO: 246049707
| LCCN: 98903113 | VIAF : 151453884

George M. Soares Prabhu, SJ

(1929-11-17 - 1995-07-22)

https://en.wikiquote.org/wiki/Soares-Prabhu,_George

ISSN 0097-2339

